

Computer-Based Platform for Phase Contrast Tomosynthesis: Targeting an Application for Breast Imaging

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Abstract— This paper presents a computer-based system dedicated to x-ray phase contrast (PhC) imaging research. It consists of two main modules: (a) a module for generation of x-ray PhC images from computational phantoms and (b) a module for image reconstruction. The module for generation of x-ray images consists of submodules dedicated to modelling of computational phantoms, modelling the image acquisition geometry and formation of x-ray images. The module for image reconstruction is a software tool, based on an in-house built reconstruction techniques class library, which is a dedicated object-oriented library for x-ray based applications. The computer-based system is tested for its feasibility to generate correctly PhC projection images and to reconstruct from them, considering a breast tomosynthesis setup. Two computational phantoms were designed for the simulations: a 4 cm thick polymethyl methacrylate phantom with air channels and a 2 cm thick rectangular polystyrene flask filled with epoxy resin mixture. Images in a tomosynthesis mode were generated and tomograms were calculated by using the reconstruction module. Simulations were validated with the help of experimental study conducted at beamline ID17, ESRF. Results show good visual agreement between simulated and experimentally obtained images. The platform, after its complete evaluation, may be useful in studying new x-ray imaging techniques based on phase contrast. Applications are foreseen also in education and training.

Keywords— Computer-based platform, modelling and simulation, phase contrast imaging, tomosynthesis, image reconstruction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast tomosynthesis (BT) is a three-dimensional (3D) x-ray imaging technique that uses multiple low dose x-ray image projections taken around the breast and 3D reconstruction techniques to further obtain a 3D image of the breast. The experience during clinical trials as well as the early clinical implementation of BT showed that the combined use of BT and digital mammography is associated with improved outcomes for screening and diagnostic imaging. Results from the TOMMY trial, demonstrated that the specificity of BT and two-dimensional (2D) mammography was better than the later technique alone but there was only marginal improvement in sensitivity [1].

Phase contrast (PhC) x-ray imaging can add more information on tissue structure, as for example improvement in the edge visibility. PhC x-ray imaging is a technique based not only on x-ray attenuation but also on the x-ray phase change related to diffraction and refraction effects during x-ray propagation in the tissue. The complex refractive index $n(\lambda)$ of a tissue at wavelength λ , is the tissue property of interest. It is usually denoted as $n(\lambda) = 1 - \delta(\lambda) + i\beta(\lambda)$, where $i^2 = -1$, β is the absorption index and δ determines the phase changes [2]. At wavelengths used for 2D and tomographic (3D) breast x-ray imaging, δ is between 10^{-6} and 10^{-8} , and the ratio δ/β is as large as 10^3 to 10^5 . Integrating the values of β and δ along the direction of propagation of an x-ray beam, the total beam attenuation and the total change in its phase can be computed.

The conventional (absorption based) radiography only relies on the imaginary component β . PhC imaging exploits the x-ray intensity changes arising from the phase changes (due to the real component δ) in the tissues. Once the relationship between signal intensity on the detector and local phase changes in tissues is inverted via appropriate algorithms, pure phase imaging is possible, i.e. 2D or 3D imaging of the phase map in the irradiated tissue.

Studies with planar PhC imaging have shown that visibility of small and thin details, not visible in absorption images, become detectable as a result of this edge enhancement effect [3]. Nowadays, teams are investigating the possibility of the combined PhC and tomosynthesis technique to better differentiate low contrast tumours and to achieve strong edge enhancement of the cancer tissues [4]. To further advance in this research, the use of computer-based simulations is needed.

Aim of this paper is to present a dedicated computer-based platform for PhC breast tomosynthesis and to demonstrate its capability for volumetric reconstructions from PhC projection images, obtained in free propagation mode. To the knowledge of the authors, this is done for first time. The intended application of the platform is in the field of the breast imaging research.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Simulation of PhC tomosynthesis is related to the generation of projection images along a limited angular arc using a phase contrast imaging arrangement. Subsequently, these projection images are used to reconstruct the content of the scanned volume. In the development of the PhC tomosynthesis, we used two in-house created computer-based platforms (also described below) and modified them accordingly to include 1) proper simulation of projection images along a limited arc and PhC arrangement, and 2) reconstruction of 3D volumes from PhC images.

The PhC computer-based platform

a. Generation of PhC images

Phase contrast imaging simulation was performed using the in-house developed software application [5]. This software tool allows simulation of several x-ray imaging acquisition geometries: radiography, tomosynthesis, circular and helical CT. It consists of three main modules: 1) Module for phantom modelling, where phantoms are modelled based on solid geometry and voxel based approaches. In case of solid

geometry, simple uniform geometrical shapes with user-defined dimensions, location, orientation and composition are used. An example is shown in figure 1a, where a breast software phantom, which contains thousands of water spheres with diameters between 1 mm and 15 mm, is presented. 2) Module for acquisition geometry modelling, where isocentric and partial isocentric rotational geometries, as well as radiography and mammography are modelled. Common parameters of the simulated geometry include distances from the source to the center of rotation and to the detector (SID, SDD), gantry acquisition arc and angle step, as well as imaging and beam parameters. Figure 1b shows an example of a tomosynthesis acquisition protocol model. 3) Module for image formation modelling, where PhC images are obtained with simulation of x-ray photon transport through the phantom, based on the Fresnel-Kirchhoff diffraction theory. This module has been appropriately modified in order to generate planar images using different PhC geometry setups.

b. Reconstruction algorithms

Another in-house developed software platform is used. This software tool is based on the RTCL: Reconstruction Techniques Class Library [6], which is a dedicated object-

Fig 1: Computer-based platform dedicated to PhC tomosynthesis. Main functionalities are module for phantom modelling, module for modelling the geometry acquisition and module for image reconstructions; (a) a software breast phantom created by the use of the phantom modelling module; (b) an example for modelling tomosynthesis acquisition (SID – source to center of rotation distance, SDD – source to detector distance) and (c) a screenshot from the module dedicated to image reconstructions.

oriented library for x-ray based applications (figure 1c). This platform has been properly adjusted in order to be used with PhC projection images. By using this platform, two basic tasks can be performed: 1) fast development of known image reconstruction algorithms based on various projection data from common image acquisition setups (e.g. CT and tomosynthesis), and 2) programming and testing of new reconstruction techniques, using modified or new projection acquisition trajectories.

A. Use of the PhC computer-based platform

In this section, the use of the computer platform for testing the reconstruction algorithm for PhC tomosynthesis is demonstrated. Specifically, the platform was used to generate PhC projection images in a tomosynthesis setup, and then subsequently to use these images with a filtered back-projection algorithm to reconstruct the volume of interest. For this purpose, two phantoms were modelled with the Phantom Modelling Module: (a) a simple phantom – a 4cm thick slab of a polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) material and (b) a 2cm thick slab of epoxy resin material. The first phantom also contained four cylinders filled with air, hav-

ing diameters of 1 mm, arranged at different planes, as shown in figure 2b. The second phantom was with size of 4cm×2cm×4cm and contained about 27000 air voids modelled as spheres with radius randomly sampled between 0.05mm and 0.6mm. The high contrast of the imaged object was preferred for this first trial.

Tomosynthesis acquisition setup was simulated by implementing isocentric acquisition geometry. In this case, the x-ray tube and the detector rotate in a plane, synchronously and about a fixed central axis. This geometry is described with the two distances SID and SDD (shown in fig. 1b), which were set to 144m and 155m respectively. The acquisition arc was from -32° to $+32^\circ$ with an angular step of 4° . During this rotation, 17 high-resolution projection images of size 10000 x 10000 pixels and pixel size of $5\mu\text{m}$ were simulated. Subsequently, each high-resolution image was down-sampled to an image of the same resolution (pixel size of $47\mu\text{m}$) as the resolution of the experimental images. Incident beam energy was set to 50 keV.

For comparison purposes, an experimental study similar to the simulation one was carried out earlier. The experiment was conducted at the beamline ID17 of the European

Fig 2: Phantoms used in the study: (a) a PMMA phantom with dimensions 6cm×6cm×4cm and (c) a rectangular polystyrene flask with size 6cm×4cm×2.0cm filled with an epoxy resin mixture and thousands of air voids; (b, d) software models of the physical phantoms, approximating the physical and geometrical characteristics of the material as close as possible; (e) experimental arrangement at beamline ID17. ESRF. Grenoble.

Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF). Incident energy was 50 keV. The detector was taper optics FReLoN 2k CCD camera, with a pixel size of 47 μm and a field-of-view 95mm \times 95mm. This detector was placed at a distance of 11m away from the end surface of the imaged phantom (i.e. at 155m away from the source). The PMMA phantom was arranged on a scanning stage as shown in figure 2c that could rotate and move vertically. 17 projection images with size of 2048 x 1003 pixels in the angular scan range from -32° to $+32^\circ$ were obtained, similarly to the simulation case. Tomosynthesis images were reconstructed using filtered backprojection algorithm by the reconstruction platform. The in-plane reconstructed voxel size was set to 43.6 μm . Slice thickness was set to 0.1mm. Prior to reconstruction, projection images were pre-processed with a modified ramp filter kernel. The same procedure was repeated for the epoxy resin phantom (figure 2c, d) and incident energy of 35 keV.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows side by side projection and reconstruction images obtained by simulations (first row of images) and from the experimental study (second row of images) with the software and physical PMMA phantom. The first column (a) in figure 3 shows projection images corresponding to 0° rotation according to the geometrical setup. These two projection images were obtained with a detector placed just behind the phantom (i.e. no PhC effect is observed). The

second column (b) in figure 3 shows the corresponding simulated and experimental (lower row) projection images when the detector was placed 11 m away from the object. In the last two columns (c) in figure 3, reconstructed tomosynthesis images, parallel to the planar image in figure 3a, b and cutting the air available channels are shown.

A good agreement between reconstructed images obtained from simulations and experimental study is demonstrated in terms of visual reproducibility. As seen from figure 3, for both, absorption and PhC projection transmission images (fig. 3a, b), at 0° there is a complete overlapping of two cylinders (1 and 4 in figure 2b). By contrast and as targeted, on tomosynthesis reconstructed images, all four air channels are fully separated. In addition, the edge enhancement effect, observed on the projection image in figure 3b is fully preserved on tomosynthesis image.

Figure 4 shows side by side projection and reconstruction images obtained by simulations (images in 4b and 4d) and from the experimental study (images in 4a and 4c) with the software and physical epoxy resin phantoms, respectively. This type of phantoms is highly inhomogeneous, due to the several thousand air voids, which were created in the epoxy volume. Figure 4a, b shows the projection images obtained during experimentation and simulation tasks. As shown in these images, there is an overlap of lots of air voids on the planar images. Due to the phase contrast setup, an edge enhancement effect is observed: the edges of the projected spheres are well defined. The limitation however, is related with the planar imaging and unavailability to resolve the

Fig. 3: Comparison of (a, b) projection and (c) reconstruction images of the PMMA phantom with the four air channels obtained through simulations (first row) and experimental study (second row). Images in (a) are obtained in absorption mode, while images in (b-c) are obtained in PhC mode.

different objects and to specify in 3D their position. Figure 4c, d shows reconstructed tomosynthesis images obtained from experimental and simulation projection images, respectively.

Fig. 4: Comparison of (a, b) projection and (c, d) reconstruction images of the epoxy resin phantom with air voids obtained through simulations (b,d) and experimental study (a,c). Images are obtained in a PhC mode.

The comparison of planar and tomosynthesis images shows that the edge effect observed in planar images is well preserved on tomosynthesis images. The superposition of internal details (air voids) in this phantom produces a complex texture background in projection images (figure 4a,b), while in reconstructed images (figure 4c,d) there is a partial removal of details that are not in the focused planes. The later results in improved visibility for the details positioned in the corresponding plane, well defined object dimensions and location.

Besides the research aspects of use of the presented computer-based platform, the later may turn out to be very useful tool for training of Medical Physics Experts in the field of Diagnostic and Interventional Radiology [7, 8].

CONCLUSIONS

A computer-based platform dedicated to x-ray phase contrast tomosynthesis has been successfully tested to visually reproduce phase contrast tomosynthesis images. The first results showed the potential of PhC tomosynthesis for resolving successfully the complexity of a highly structured background in the x-ray imaging of thick and inhomogeneous phantoms, at least in the case shown of high-contrast details. Next step is to validate these results quantitatively. The use of physical and software phantoms dedicated to breast imaging is also foreseen for further validation and research experimentation as well as in education and training of biomedical engineers and medical physicists.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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